

BROMINATION OF OXYMETHYLENE METHYL ETHYL KETONE AND OF OXYMETHYLENE ACETOPHENONE

BY R. R. AGARWAL, S. M. GUPTA AND S. S. DESHPANDE

Oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone and oxymethylene acetophenone have been brominated in free condition and in the form of sodium compound respectively.

Bromination of oxymethylene ketones (formyl ketones) (II) derived from ketones (I) has been attempted only in few cases. It is carried out by adding bromine to the oxymethylene ketone, neutralised with caustic soda. Bromo-oxymethylene camphor and bromo-oxymethylene menthone are formed in this way (cf. Bruhl, *Ber.*, 1904, 37, 2175, 2176). The structure (III) has been ascribed to these bromo compounds.

Bromination of oxymethylene *cyclohexanone* was, on the other hand, effected with the unneutralised ketone in ether solution by Mehta, Kaushal and Deshpande (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1946, 23, 43) and the bromination product was obtained as an unstable solid, melting at 88-90°.

The bromination of oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone (II, R=R'=Me) has been carried out in unneutralised condition and a bromo derivative (III, R=R'=Me) has been obtained as a fairly stable solid melting at 143°.

Keto-enolic systems $-\text{CO}-\overset{|}{\text{CH}}-\text{CO}-\text{X}$ seem to differ from aldo-enolic systems $-\text{CO}-\overset{|}{\text{CH}}-\text{CO}-\text{H}$ when the behaviour of their sodium compounds with halogens is considered. Thus, whereas sodium acetylacetone reacts with iodine (1 atom) to form 3 : 4-diacetylhexane-dione (2 : 5) (IV)

sodium oxymethylene menthone (V) gives with bromine (2 atoms) bromo-oxymethylene menthone (VI) (Bruhl, *loc. cit.*).

We have found that oxymethylene acetophenone (II R=Ph ; R'=H) behaves exactly similarly. Its bromination has been effected by suspending its sodium compound in ether and adding to it bromine (2 atoms). The bromo compound (III, R=Ph ; R'=H) is a remarkably stable solid melting at 106°. Direct bromination of oxymethylene acetophenone is difficult as the free ketone readily undergoes self-condensation to 1 : 3 : 5-tribenzoylbenzene (Claisen and Stylos, *Ber.*, 1888, 21, 1145).

EXPERIMENTAL

Bromo-oxymethylene Methyl Ethyl Ketone.—Oxymethylene methyl ethyl ketone (7g.), prepared from methyl ethyl ketone, alcohol-free sodium ethylate and ethyl formate, was dissolved in dry ether and the solution cooled by ice. Bromine (2 atoms), suspended in dry ether, was gradually added keeping the temperature at 0°. A white solid began to separate. In one experiment it was observed that if more than two atoms of bromine were added the solid which first separated again dissolved and on removal of the solvent a brown syrup was left which evolved hydrobromic acid. When exactly two atoms of bromine were added, a white solid was formed which was filtered at the pump and repeatedly washed with small amounts of dry ether, yield 7g. It could not be crystallised. It melts at 143°. (Found : Br, 44.1. $C_8H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 44 per cent). The bromo-oxymethylene ketone reduces Fehling's solution on warming

Bromo-oxymethylene Acetophenone.—The sodium compound of oxymethylene acetophenone was formed when acetophenone, condensed with ethyl formate in presence of sodium in ether, was filtered at the pump and washed with dry ether. The sodium compound was suspended in carbon tetrachloride and bromine (2 atoms), dissolved in the same solvent, was added gradually to the suspension, kept at 0°. The sodium bromide was filtered off and from the filtrate the solvent was removed. A thick syrup was left which immediately solidified. Crystallised from acetic acid the bromo compound melts at 106°. (Found : Br, 35.5. $C_9H_7O_2Br$ requires Br, 35.2 per cent). The bromo-oxymethylene ketone gives acid reactions due to the persistence of aldo-enolic system in it. It dissolves in dilute alkaline solutions from which it is reprecipitated by acids.